

ESD RISKS IN SPACE FOR WIRES AND CABLES

Wires and cables used in Space are susceptible to initiate electrostatic discharges (ESD) under certain conditions. These ESD phenomena are mainly caused by the use of excellent electrical material insulation layers and their ability to store and build-up electrostatic charges due to their intrinsic high resistivity.

The incoming charged particles can build-up inside dielectrics up to material "breakdown" threshold levels leading to electrical arcs discharged into nearby sensitive circuits.

Photo: ESA EURECA satellite solar array sustained ESD arc damage (Credits: ESA)

INNOVATIVE ANTISTATIC WIRES CONCEPT

All standard and qualified wires and cables for Space applications are composed of excellent electrical insulation materials with volume resistivities in the range of 10^{16} to 10^{21} ohm.cm (PTFE, PFA, FEP, ETFE, PEEK, Polyimides...)

An innovative approach explored by Axon' and supported by ESA activity ITT AO/17877/14/NL/RA to reduce the ESD risk for wires and cables was to replace these highly insulating dielectrics with "leaky" materials. It allows for a fast enough evacuation of incoming charged particles to the nearest conductive layer.

MAIN OBJECTIVES AND CHALLENGES

- Replace highly insulating dielectrics with « leaky » materials
- Insulation properties target based on ESA, NASA and JAXA Space Charging Standards and latest literature results on this topic
- Development of new material formulations and processing compatible with Space environment
- Study the Influence of each processing stages and measurements methods on materials properties and final antistatic wires performances

DEVELOPMENT RESULTS

New modified Antistatic materials formulations and Wires Prototypes with controlled volume resistivities in the range of $[10^7 - 10^{15}]$ ohm.cm have been successfully developed and characterized.

ESD-type classification of insulation materials

Based on ESA ECSS-E-ST-20-06C

Apparent volume resistivity depends on applied voltage:

- Below 100V (current spacecraft power sub-systems 28-100V max): $\rho > 10^{11}$ ohm.cm
- Between 100-250V: $\rho = [10^8 - 10^{11}]$ ohm.cm
- Reversible behaviour (when voltage decreases)
- Maintained stable volume resistivity value in the antistatic range from at least -80 to +160°C (measured range)
- Excellent mechanical properties (similar to ESCC 3901/012)

This innovative miniature, low mass solution doesn't require complex grounding compared to multilayers cables with only a semi-conductive outer-layer.

Volume resistivity range

of new antistatic ETFE wire W4825M1 as a function of applied voltage (dc) and testing time duration

ANTISTATIC WIRES PROTOTYPES

These new Axon' "smart antistatic" wires prototypes are now available to the Space community.

Next steps toward a full space ESCC-type qualification require investigation of the charge decay behaviour of these new antistatic wires when exposed to a GEO-like radiation spectra in vacuum and thermal cycling between -150°C and +150°C. This will confirm the effective Space-ESD resistance of this innovative cable solution and materials.

WIRE PROTOTYPE REFERENCE: W4825M1

Conductor		Type	SPC AWG 24
Wire insulation system		Insulation material	Modified antistatic ETFE
		Finished wire Ø (mm)	≈ 1.10 mm
Spark test	ESCC 3901 style	Max voltage	800V - PASS
Voltage test			500V - PASS
Abrasion	ESC 3901/012 requirements	Minimum 100 cycles	> 2000 cycles
Cut-through		Minimum 40 N	> 150 N
Blocking		200°C - no sticking	PASS
Shrinkage		Max 2mm	< 0.120 mm
Tensile properties		No standard specification	
		Stress at break (MPa)	> 35 MPa
		Strain at break (%)	> 250 %
Insulation bulk resistivity		Volume resistivity (ohm.cm) based on ASTM D257 DC voltage after 60 sec	
		At 10 V	2.38E+15
		At 50 V	1.02E+15
		At 100 V	8.34E+14
		At 200 V	1.26E+13
Cold bend test -80°C 4 hours		Initial volume resistivity (ohm.cm)	
		At 10 V	5.71E+14
		At 50 V	2.03E+13
		At 250 V	5.15E+11
		After cold bend (ohm.cm)	
At 10 V	3.04E+13		
At 50 V	2.08E+12		
At 250 V	1.86E+10		
Final voltage test		At 250 V	PASS
Accelerated thermal ageing +230°C 120 hours		Initial volume resistivity (ohm.cm)	
		At 10 V	2.48E+15
		At 50 V	1.54E+15
		At 250 V	2.38E+12
		After thermal ageing (ohm.cm)	
At 10 V	3.13E+12		
At 50 V	7.66E+10		
At 250 V	1.52E+08		
Final voltage test		At 250 V	PASS